

Teaching and Learning Experiences in Letran's Partial Implementation of Outcomes Based Education

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Abstract— In the Philippines, there is a shift in the curriculum from traditional teaching into Outcomes -Based Education (OBE). It is described as a lifelong learning curriculum aligned to the demand of the employers who supported international and global standards. Among the institutions responding to the need in upgrading the bar in education is Colegio De San Juan De Letran (CSJL). In this study, the researchers explored the relationships of the four components of curriculum. The study used descriptive method. The respondents are twenty-nine (29) CLAS faculty members and 620 students enrolled in the College of Liberal Arts and Sciences. Researchers analyzed that data collected through multiple iterations. Based on the results, the researchers concluded that CLAS faculty members have a positive attitude towards an outcomes-based educational approach and claimed to know how to do OBE in their respective classes. However, when it comes to CLAS faculty member's knowledge about the assessment techniques for OBE, they felt that it is inadequate. CLAS faculty members feel that trainings provided in the past were not enough. It is important to establish high and uniform academic standards, accompanied by a system of accountability for the successful implementation of OBE. The Colegio should have a continuous and sustainable monitoring of the implementation of OBE during its infancy.

Keywords— OBE, Teaching and Learning, OBE Curriculum, Perception.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the Philippines, there is a shift in the curriculum from traditional teaching into Outcomes -Based Education (OBE). It is described as a lifelong learning curriculum aligned to the demand of the employers who supported international and global standards. In OBE, it is expected that there is a transmission of expert knowledge in building learner competencies. (CMO No. 46, series 2012, Policy-Standard to Enhance Quality Assurance (QA) in Philippine Higher Education, Section 11, p.4).

In OBE, the competencies are written in the curriculum are aligned to the competencies needed by the employers. In this way, jobs can easily move from one country to another, hence, multi-national employers will not have hesitation in relocating jobs in order to maximize its advantage (Primer on the Quality Assurance and Institutional Sustainability Assessment of HEIs, Annex 4 of Guidelines for the Implementation of CMO 46, series 2012, p.14). If the competencies and international standards are followed, Philippines and other countries can offer quality degree programs and world-class standards in every institution. At the same time, graduates can face the

global arena and compete into regional and international graduates too.

The OBE curriculum is not only beneficial to the graduates but helps the social, economic and development needed by the country (Ibid, p.15). For these reasons, Commission on Higher Education (CHED) supports all Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) to engage in the process of promoting a culture of quality and developing mature institutions. Moreover, CHED encourages HEIs to be flexible in translating the policies, programs and systems leading to quality graduates.

To support the implementation of OBE in the Philippines, CHED started issuing memo to revise the current curriculum in higher education. It started in CHED curriculum revision highlight in 2008, transforming content-based to competency curriculum or outcomes-based curriculum. In 2012 CHED issued another memo (memorandum order no.37) on policies, standards and guidelines in the establishment of an outcomes-based education (OBE) system in higher education institutions offering engineering programs. It was followed by the CHED memorandum order no. 46 in the same year, issuing standard to enhance quality assurance (QA) in Philippine higher education through outcomes-based and typology-based QA.

The idea OBE began in the 1980s which adhere closely to the behaviorists principles on competency movement particularly on attitudes, emotions and values (Spady, 1988; 1994). Although, these principles on competency are important, Spady (1994, pp.55-60) mentioned that these preconditions for outcomes rather than outcomes themselves. These preconditions are called "goals" which are not directly observable and could not be included as specification of an outcome. Three premises and four principles cover OBE paradigm: 1.all students can learn and succeed but not on the same day and not in the same way; 2. successful learning promotes even more successful learning; and 3. Schools control the conditions that affect directly affect successful learning (Spady, 1994)

At the same time, it is anchored by four "power principles" which are: a. clarity of focus on culminating outcomes of significance; 2. Expanded opportunity and support for learning success; 3. High expectations for all to succeed; and 4. Design down from your ultimate, culminating outcomes.

The clarity of focus involves teachers to build thoughtful, knowledgeable selections in creating instruction to facilitate the achievement of students and their intended learning

outcomes. Expanded opportunity means that all learners are exposed to different and appropriate instructional strategies and additional learning opportunities in order to become successful (Killen, 2000). A high expectation reinforces the prior learning of the students in order to heighten their self-confidence and motivation. Lastly, in designing down, the teachers start in identifying exit outcomes and are followed by the needed learning that students need to achieve.

Hodges (2010) identified relevant unresolved issues in OBE such as lack of clearly defined and assessable outcomes which is impossible to accomplish to individual learner. It is also important to provide concise learning outcomes for standardization purposes. Another issue in OBE is that individual teacher and learner are more or less unrepresented, and more of an object of regulation. The rationale of adopting OBE, is almost entirely expressed in terms of assessment and accountability, with little direct link to teaching and learning (Cooke et.al, 2010). Hodges' analysis of the main benefits of OBE is, likewise, dominated by the discourses of assessment and accountability (Hodges, 2010). However, other researchers believe that OBE was an advocacy that reduces value, insight and judgment because the affective, social, cultural, aesthetic and ethic learning processes are not included at the core of education and the emphasis is only on the product of education.

Although other researchers critique OBE, in the field of instruction, Jackson (2002) believes that it is a student-centered approach to education that focuses on the intended learning outcomes resulting from teaching. Three components that comprise an outcome-based approach into learning are: an explicit statement of learning intent expressed as outcomes which reflect educational aims, purposes and values; the process or strategy to enable the intended learning to be achieved and demonstrated (curriculum, teaching, learning, assessment and support and guidance methods); and criteria for assessing learning which are aligned to the intended outcome.

Due to the nature of OBE, it is also essential that teachers are knowledgeable in various teaching strategies to be used in their discipline. The need to know their students in terms of IQ, learning styles and multiple intelligences can assist teachers in identifying appropriate teaching strategies to achieve the expected institutional, program and learning outcomes set by the institutions.

In OBE, it is also important to consider the essential knowledge and skills that students are expected to have learned in order to ensure that learning ultimately happens. In the area of assessment, students and teachers are expected to picture out what is important for students to be able to do especially in organizing the curriculum, instruction and assessment to achieve learning (Spady, 1994).

Outcomes based approach to assessment has distinct features, namely: a. emphasis on output or end products; b. uses criterion reference; c. continuous; d. use formative and summative assessment; e. concern with reliability and fairness issues; f. valid; g. integrated assessment; and h. aligned to the intended student outcomes.

Opposite to lecture inputs, the focus of OBE is the application of the knowledge acquired and demonstration of the acquired skills and values through outputs or end products. It is equally important that students are aware on how they are clearly assessed and how to successful achieve in the class within specific context.

Instead of a norm reference, the use of OBE prevents the comparison of students with one another. Students are assessed based on the judgment made about by the learners against set criteria. Although grades vary, students are graded whether they have satisfied from the set criteria in class. The criterion used is based on the outcomes set for a course, which is also aligned to the program and institutional outcomes.

In assessing the learning of the students in OBE, both formative and summative are included. The formative assessment is used to chart the learning progress of the students towards achieving the specific outcomes and achieve competence. At the same time, formal assessment is also administered at the end of the program. The criteria for formal assessment is also set and given to the students for their judgment, reference and guide for the assessment tasks.

A set rubric is also given to the students in order to maintain the consistency of measuring the output submitted by the teacher. The rubrics are made by the teacher and agreed upon by the students. The planning, developing and administering the assessment tool is monitored by the teacher and made it available also to the students. The criterion in the rubrics is specified to maintain the consistency of assessing the outputs of the students. All criterions that are not included in the rubrics are not graded in order to maintain the validity of the assessment as well.

In OBE, the practical and reflective competences are also incorporated in assessment. In this way, teachers can scrutinize the overall purpose of the qualification in each program through portfolio or collection of his/her work in his/her subject. Lastly, the assessment is aligned to the intended graduate outcomes of the institution.

Among the institutions responding to the need in upgrading the bar in education is Colegio De San Juan De Letran (CSJL). Among the colleges in the colegio, the College of Liberal Arts and Sciences (CLAS) initiates the partial implementation of OBE in the seven programs under it, namely, AB Advertising, AB Broadcasting, AB Communication, AB Journalism, AB Legal Management, AB Political Science, and BS Psychology. In the partial implementation of OBE, all professors handling the subject under the said programs are required to implement OBE in paper, practice and pedagogy.

This study explores and analyzes the partial implementation of OBE under CLAS. Specifically, it sought to: 1. determine the perception of students and teachers towards OBE; 2. describe the partial implementation of OBE in the area of: a. curriculum and instruction; b. teaching strategies; and c. assessment.; 3. identify and describe of the challenges and success of partial implementation of OBE in CLAS; and 4. draw out implications in the implementation of OBE policies.

Fig. 1. Conceptual Diagram of the Study

In this study, the researchers explored the relationships of the four components of curriculum. The researchers analyzed the attitude of the CLAS students and teachers. The syllabus, the intended outcome and instruction were explored to connect the relationships of each component in an outcome based education in CLAS. The attitude is focused on knowledge, beliefs, feelings, readiness and acceptance level of CLAS faculty. The syllabi were explored to verify if the learning outcomes are aligned to the institutional goal, teaching and learning method, and assessment.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research Design

The study used descriptive method. It is used to describe a population or phenomenon being studied. The researchers describe the attitude, perception, teaching and learning method, and assessment of the partial implementation of OBE in CLAS. The design includes gathering, analyzing, exploring and tabulating data.

Research Respondents

The respondents are twenty-nine (29) CLAS faculty members and 620 students enrolled in the College of Liberal Arts and Sciences. The student respondents were randomly selected.

Instrument and Procedure

In order to analyze the perception of teachers and students, participants were given an expert validated questionnaire. The questionnaire consists of demographic profile, teaching and learning method and assessment. To measure the knowledge, beliefs, feelings, readiness and acceptance level of CLAS Faculty, adopted instrument from Ortega & Ortega-Dela Cruz (2016) was used.

Syllabi were collected and observations of classes were done to describe the partial implementation of OBE in the area of curriculum and instruction. Interview and focus group discussion to teachers and students were conducted to supplement the observations of classes and classroom walkthrough.

Monitoring of assessment is observed on how teachers develop the tools towards their students and their output. Rubrics used in class were collected to ensure and verify the

development of assessment tools for the students. In order to confirm the developing process in assessing students, interview to the students and teachers were employed.

Direct evaluation and observation in the development of the tools were followed to document how the teacher develop the tool and if the assessment tool is aligned to the intended program and graduate outcomes. Lastly, in identifying and describing the challenges and success of the partial implementation of OBE, one-on-one interview and focus group discussion were employed.

Interview was conducted in varied approaches (informal interview to semi-structured to structured interviews. Artifacts and text including written protocols, charts, flow sheets, educational handouts, syllabi and rubrics were collected for analysis.

Researchers analyzed that data collected through multiple iterations. The process of iteration was involved sets and series of questions that is designed to generate a model regarding the partial OBE implementation. The generative questions may lead to the first iteration of theoretical sampling. The comparative process was continued until the researchers reach saturation. Saturation is the point at which there are no new ideas and insights emerging from the data. In this stage, the researcher sees strong repetition in the themes observed and articulated. The analysis of the data involves three levels namely a. open coding; b. axial coding; and c. selective coding.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results and discussion of this study. The results of the study are presented in such a way that the objectives were previously presented. This section is divided into three parts: a. Knowledge, beliefs, feelings, readiness and acceptance level of CLAS faculty towards OBE; b. Perceptions of teachers and students on teaching strategies, evaluation and assessment; c. Classroom Observation

Table 1. OBE Training of CLAS Faculty

	Frequency	Percentage (%)
None	1	3.4
Not Adequate	5	17.2
Adequate	20	69.0
Too much	3	10.3
Total	29	100.0

Table 1 shows the frequency and percentage of OBE training of CLAS faculty. More than half of the population of the faculty reported that they have adequate training (69%). There were few who perceived that they have too much training (10.3%). While 17.2 % agreed that they do not have adequate training and only 3.4% mentioned that there is no OBE training given to them at all.

Table 2 shows the knowledge, beliefs, feelings, readiness and acceptance of CLAS faculty members towards an outcomes-based educational approach. Based from the gathered data, selected CLAS faculty members have a fairly positive attitude towards an outcomes-based educational approach. In its partial OBE implementation, majority of the participants agreed (2.86 = Agree) that they know how to

conduct an OBE approach in their class by aligning theoretical principles to relevant job-related skills and knowledge. However, when it comes to their knowledge about the assessment techniques for OBE, most of them declared that it is inadequate (2.4 = Disagree).

Table 2. Knowledge, beliefs, feelings, readiness and acceptance level of CLAS Faculty

ITEM	Weighted Mean	Verbal Description
Knowledge		
1. I know where to start with an OBE approach in my class.	2.9	Agree
2. I am able to align the world of learning with the world of work.	3.3	Agree
3. I know how to facilitate an outcomes-based class.	2.8	Agree
4. I am equipped to establish a satisfactory OBE classroom climate, providing cooperative, well directed and purposeful activities.	2.9	Agree
5. My knowledge of the assessment techniques for OBE is adequate.	2.4	Disagree
Beliefs		
6. I believe that most OBE approaches prepare the student better for the workplace.	3.1	Agree
7. I believe OBE will raise the standards of students' academic achievements in their course.	3.1	Agree
8. I believe that an OBE approach to learning would require more liaisons with industry.	3.2	Agree
9. I believe that OBE will allow me to be more flexible in employing a variety of teaching methods in my class.	3.2	Agree
10. I believe that OBE approach will provide all students with equal educational opportunities.	2.7	Agree
Feelings		
11. I feel that OBE approaches require more responsibilities from Academics than content driven approaches.	3.1	Agree
12. I feel that an OBE approach to learning would not be a waste of time.	2.9	Agree
13. I feel that traditional pen and paper tests to assess student competencies do not always benefit the students.	3.1	Agree
14. I feel that OBE approach is the best learning approach	2.8	Agree
15. I feel that OBE will provide me with an opportunity to ensure that all learners achieve success	2.8	Agree
Readiness		
16. I have conflict of interests between an OBE approach and the content approach of learning.	2.3	Disagree
17. I am more interested in presenting OBE approach than content driven approach in my classes	2.9	Agree
18. Knowing that OBE is mandatory motivates me to do more preparation.	3	Agree
19. I believe that my interest in OBE approach to learning enhances my ability to be a good facilitator.	3.3	Agree
20. I believe that large classes at Letran (more than 40 students per group) will hinder the successful implementation of OBE.	3.7	Strongly Agree
Acceptance Level		
21. My daily schedule allows for adequate preparation time of OBE approaches.	2.8	Agree
22. I have the available resources to present my lessons using OBE approach.	2.7	Agree
23. I believe that my experience in teaching will help me to adapt to an OBE approach of learning	3.2	Agree
24. I do a lot of subject-related reading in order to improve my knowledge and understanding of OBE approaches.	3	Agree
25. I have received adequate training in OBE.	2.2	Disagree

When teachers were asked what are the usual teaching strategies they employed in the classroom, participants often use lecture/discussions, activities done inside the classroom and/or inquiry teaching where the teacher poses questions to be answered by the students. Sometimes, the faculty members also make use of internet, computers, and other audio-visual materials. Assessment strategies used were also asked. On a regular basis, educators of the CLAS faculty use examinations and group work. They also use essays, experiments, performance-based activities, portfolios and projects.

Although the participants may have affirmed that they are knowledgeable in implementing OBE in their classes, it can be observed that the teaching and learning strategies they used in their respective classes remained the same with that of the traditional teacher-centered approach. This issue is consistent with the study of Barman, Laksov and Silen (2014) wherein the outcomes-based education as a policy have resulted in local variations not only on how it was interpreted but on how it was enacted by teachers. Their results concluded that teachers' perceptions of teaching-learning and what they actually do in the classroom are not always associated.

However, the study of Barman et.al (2014) contradicts with the result of Lee and Cheung (2015) and stresses that diverse perception of teaching among educators leads to different interpretations of OBE. Thus, it is important for the management to internalize such paradigm shift in the organizational culture in order to avoid a "face of compliance". Bandura's Triadic Reciprocal Causation can help shed light in understanding this challenge. As postulated, the model explains that the interaction among environment, behavior and person causes human action (Feist & Feist, 2013). The person in this context represents factors like the person's physical attributes and cognitive factors such as memory, reasoning and judgment. The relative strength of the 3 factors varies with the person and with the situation. In this case, the person is the teacher's perception and understanding about OBE. The environment is the OBE policy and the behavior would be teachers' implementation of OBE. The theory enlightens the issue why there are different interpretations of the said educational approach. It is most probable that the teachers' understanding of OBE (the person) strongly influence teaching effectiveness and the environment is less influential (OBE policy).

Similarly, majority of the participants believe (3.06 = Agree) that OBE will raise the standard of students' academic achievement in their respective courses which can strengthen the connections with the industry. They also believe (3.02 = Agree) that OBE will give educators the flexibility in using different teaching methods in the class. Furthermore, the new educational approach will allow equal educational opportunities for all students.

In the initial implementation of OBE, most of the CLAS faculty members, students' performance increased greatly. During the focus group discussion (FGD), some teachers observed that their students became more active, engaged and serious in their studies because students have interest in various activities. It was also believed that OBE will help enhance students' critical thinking, time management and productivity as the new approach is student-centered. This is consistent with Malan (2000) that OBE is a transformational approach because it allows learners to interact with the sources of knowledge, reconstruct it and take responsibility for their learning outcomes. The role of the teachers is more as facilitators than a source of information. Sullivan and Downey (2015) had the same realization on the success of OBE as students take ownership in learning and there was an increase in academic vigor that will lead to more academic success because of the clearly defined standards expected from them.

When it comes to the feelings associated with the OBE approach, most of the participants feel that OBE will deliver opportunities for success among all learners (2.80 = Agree). They feel that OBE is the best learning approach because the traditional assessment (pen-and-paper) does not always benefit the students. They feel satisfied with the current implementation of OBE, the students' performance, and their individual implementation of OBE in their respective classes. However, when it comes to the training they received, faculty members feel that trainings provided in the past were enough but not to make them satisfied about it.

During the FGD conducted focus on post-assessment of the quantitative measure of selected CLAS faculty members, some of the participants mentioned that students have become more dynamic. That is because students can now realize and appreciate the importance of the courses to the program and be able to apply theoretical knowledge to actual work settings. Thus, bridge the gap between the quality of graduates produced by Higher Education Institutions and the quality of employees employers look for in various industries. As mentioned by Castillo (2014), it is already an obligation for Higher Education Institutions (HEI) to conform to international standards by its ability to produce graduates that are employable not only in the Philippines but across countries.

The observation of the participants on OBE can also be viewed as an optimistic approach because it allows all students to learn and succeed on their own phase. Thus, this can minimize the stigma that if one student cannot follow the same learning phase as everyone else, s/he is incompetent. Through this principle, educators should be flexible in their teaching strategies and should not force one approach to all students. Educators, although will act more as a facilitator than a teacher, should be adept with different strategies that can cater the diverse pool of students. Higher education institutions, thus, should prepare itself, its employees and its resources in a conducive climate and culture of OBE.

When asked about their readiness in implementing OBE, majority answered that the Colegio is ready for it (3.04 = Agree). Yet, they feel that having large classes of more than 40 students per class might deter the effective implementation of OBE (3.70 = Strongly Agree). In terms of CLAS faculty members' acceptance level of OBE, most of them agreed that their schedule allows them to have an sufficient time to prepare for an OBE approach in their class (2.80 = Agree). Moreover, they do a lot of readings to improve their knowledge and understanding of OBE (3.00 = Agree). However, they also said that they have received inadequate training in OBE (2.20 = Disagree).

Since OBE is considered a paradigm shift or a "change" in educational approach in the Philippines, it can affect the existing organizational culture of an institution where organizational culture is the set of structures, routines, rules and norms that guide and constrain employee behaviors. Shifting from a teacher-centered approach to a student-centered approach requires educators to adjust their teaching practices and to learn/develop new strategies which they are not accustomed to.

Therefore, there is really a necessity for proper OBE training to teachers' professional development (Joseph, 2002). Even those teachers who have positive attitudes toward OBE mentioned the availability of resources as a need for a successful implementation of OBE (Ortega & Dela Cruz, 2016). Selected CLAS faculty members also addressed that the Colegio should provide resources that support OBE's assessment especially when it comes to the creation of rubrics.

To further understand and make light on the result, Theory of Planned behavior (Ajzen, 1991), which was originally named Theory of Reasoned Action (Ajzen & Madden, 1986),

strengthens the occurrence of the challenge about receiving trainings. It was established to understand the effects of attitudes in intentional and thoughtful behavior. It assumes that behavioral prediction (self-efficacy) is influenced by whether people believe that they can perform a certain behavior. One's action depends on whether they have the essential resources and opportunities in performing the behavior. Thus, teachers' willingness in embracing and implementing OBE is affected by their confidence in their ability to deliver "new" teaching and learning strategies. Regardless of how positive their attitude towards an outcomes-based education, their perceived behavioral control will still affect their behavioral intention of doing it. Therefore, school administrators/management should focus on teachers' training on teaching strategies relevant to OBE in order to lift up their conviction that they can successfully perform such tasks.

Perception of Students/Teachers on Teaching and Evaluation Strategies

Table 3. Perception of Teachers on Teaching and Student evaluation strategies used in OBE partial implementation (N=29)

	A		B		C		D		E		F		G		H		I		J	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Always	0	0	0	0	1	3.4	1	3.4	1	3.4	4	13.8	5	17.2	1	3.4	2	6.9	1	3.4
Often	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	6.9	9	31.0	9	31.0	5	17.2	7	24.1	1	3.4
Sometimes	13	44.8	1	3.4	1	3.4	1	3.4	1	3.4	1	3.4	1	3.4	1	3.4	1	3.4	1	3.4
Rarely	4	13.8	5	17.2	2	6.9	4	13.8	6	20.7	0	0	3	10.3	3	10.3	8	27.4	3	10.3
Never	1	3.4	65	224.1	1	3.4	1	3.4	1	3.4	1	3.4	1	3.4	1	3.4	1	3.4	20	68.9
Total	9	30.3	100	336.7	9	30.3	9	30.3	9	30.3	9	30.3	9	30.3	9	30.3	9	30.3	9	30.3

Legend:
A- Talk/Lecture; B - Individual Work; C- Small Group; D- Activity-Based Lesson; E- Discussion (class/group); F- Computer/Internet/Tablet; G- Film/YouTube/DVD/Video/Audio Tape; H- Individual/Group Presentation; I- Demonstration/Experiment/Role Play; J- Question and Answer

Based on table 3, CLAS teachers/faculty reported that they "rarely" use lecture/talk (65.5%), discussion (37.9%), and question and answer (48.3%) as a form of teaching and student evaluation strategies in an OBE setup. CLAS faculty agreed that "sometimes" they used Individual work (51.7%), Small group (41.4%), Activity-Based Lesson (41.4%), Computer/Internet/Tablet (34.5%), Film/YouTube/DVD/Video/Audio Tape (44.8%), Individual group Presentation (44.8%) and Demonstration/Experiment/Role play (44.8%) as seen in the table and supported with figure. The table also showed that CLAS faculty do not always used a single strategy in teaching and evaluating the learners which ranges from 0%-3.4%. There are some teachers who said they "never" use a specific strategy because it is not appropriate to their subject matter.

When the students were asked about the different teaching and evaluation strategies that their professor used, students reported that their professor "always" used lecture (n=417; 67.3%) and discussion (n=375; 60.5%) as seen in table 4. Students agreed that their always used Question and Answer (n=308; 49.7%), Activity-Based Lesson (n=300;

48.4%), and Computer/Internet/Tablet (n=199; 32.1%). Some students also agreed that their teachers “often” used small group (n= 175; 28.2%) and demonstration/experiment/role play (n=162; 26.1%). Students agreed also their CLAS faculty sometimes used Film/Youtube/DVD/Video/Audio Tape (n=175; 28.2%) and Individual/Group Presentation (n=240; 38.7%). However, only few students said that their teacher never used any of the teaching strategies which ranges from 7 to 50 students (1.1% to 8.1%) of the total respondents as seen in table 4 and supported with figure.

Table 4. Perception of Students in the teaching and student evaluation strategies used by Teachers in OBE partial implementation (N=620) in CLAS.

	A		B		C		D		E		F		G		H		I		J	
	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%	f	%
Always	417	67.3	209	33.7	172	27.7	300	48.4	375	60.5	199	32.1	156	25.2	172	27.7	142	22.9	308	49.7
Often	136	21.9	182	29.2	4	0.6	181	29.2	124	20	94	15.2	75	12.1	180	29	162	26.1	181	29.2
Sometimes	51	8.2	167	26.9	9	1.4	171	27.6	6	0.9	81	13.1	78	12.6	138	22.3	175	28.2	240	38.7
Rarely	9	1.5	41	6.6	52	8.4	36	5.8	29	4.7	82	13.2	111	17.9	17	2.7	94	15.2	22	3.5
Never	7	1.1	21	3.4	50	8.1	22	3.5	14	2.3	107	17.3	103	16.6	11	1.8	110	17.7	9	1.5
Total	620	100	620	100	620	100	620	100	620	100	620	100	620	100	620	100	620	100	620	100

Legend: A- Talk/Lecture; B - Individual Work; C- Small Group; D- Activity-Based Lesson; E- Discussion (class/group); F- Computer/Internet/Tablet; G- Film/Youtube/DVD/Video/Audio Tape; H- Individual/Group Presentation; I - Demonstration/Experiment/Role Play; J-Question and Answer

The perception of students contradicts the perception of the teachers towards the use of teaching strategy. Teachers admit that they rarely use lecture/talk in their classes which opposes the answers of the students that always use lecture/talk in class. It is important that the strategies used in the class is aligned to the learning outcomes of the students. According to Jenkins and Unwin (2001) in order to assert the learning outcomes, it important that the teacher communicate with the students what is precisely expected from them. Informing the students can lessen the disparity in the perception and expectation to their professors. It can help the both the students and teachers know their stand in the curriculum in an open manner (Kennedy, Hyland & Ryan, 2006). Aligning what teacher does in the learning environment and activities can help achieve the use of appropriate teaching strategies. The alignment must show coherence in the teaching strategies, learning outcomes and assessment in an educational program (Mcmahon & Thakore, 2006; Biggs, 2004).

The educational philosophy of the school and the curriculum are important in determining the appropriate teaching strategies. In this study, the researchers explored on the teaching strategies used by teachers under OBE. In an OBE curriculum, the use of problem-based approach, community based teaching and learning, individual work and student-centered approach are the recommended teaching strategies that supports OBE (Davis, 2003).

The researchers explore the subject effects of the responses of student respondents on their interest and difficulty in the subjects and teaching strategies used by the teachers. The results are shown below.

Table 5 showed the subject effect between interest of the students in the subject and teaching strategies. The result shows that there are mean differences between the interest of

the students toward the subject and teaching strategies used by the teachers particularly teacher question and activity (p<.0005) and film/youtube (p<.002). Interesting to note that other teaching strategies do not show significant differences in the mean scores between student interest and teaching strategies such as Lecture (p= .012), Individual Work (p=.034), Small Group (p=.069), Discussion (p=.016), Computer(p=.385) and demonstration (p=.065). Although the use of teaching strategies may affect the interest of the students in the subjects, still, majority of the teaching strategies do not show significant difference. Hence, varied teaching strategies in the class in an OBE setting may not be a basis in getting interests of the students in each subject.

Table 5. Tests of Between-Subjects Effects (Interest in the subject)

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	116.392 ^a	40	2.910	6.347	.000
Intercept	146.938	1	146.938	320.506	.000
Lecture/Teacher Directed	5.981	4	1.495	3.262	.012
Individual Work	4.821	4	1.205	2.629	.034
Small Group	4.015	4	1.004	2.189	.069
Discussion/ Small or Whole Class	5.643	4	1.411	3.077	.016
Activity Lesson	14.166	4	3.541	7.725	.000
Computer/ Internet/Tablet	1.909	4	.477	1.041	.385
Film/ DVD/ Youtube	7.748	4	1.937	4.225	.002
Individual/ Group Presentation	6.287	4	1.572	3.428	.009
Demonstration/Experiment/ Role Play	4.085	4	1.021	2.227	.065
Teacher- Question	22.723	4	5.681	12.391	.000
Error	265.447	579	.458		
Total	2822.000	620			
Corrected Total	381.839	619			

(DV: Interest in the Subject ; a. R Squared = .305 (Adjusted R Squared = .257))

Table 6 showed the subject effect difficulty in varied teaching strategies. The result shows that there are mean differences in the difficulty of the subjects and teaching strategies used by the professors particularly demonstration/experiment/role play (df=4; F=3.784; p<.0005), individual/group/presentation (df=4; F=4.119; p<0.005), discussion/small/whole class (df=4; 1.988; p= 0.009), small group (df=4; F=2.291; p<.001). Students reported that these strategies may influence their perception about the difficulty of the subjects. On the other hand, Lecture (p=.123), Individual work (p=.025), Activity (p=.094), Computer/Tablet (p=.074), Film (.063), and Teacher Question (p=.021) do not show significant differences in the mean difficulty of the subjects and teaching strategy. Student respondents reported that these teaching strategies are not correlated in the difficulty of the subjects.

The use of rubrics is essential in the implementation of OBE. Rubrics serve as the key to corrections or answer key to correctly perform the expected outputs and also, to further validate if the outcomes are met. Rubrics as an assessment is coherent to a set of criteria for students' work that includes descriptions of levels of performance quality on the criteria. One of the advantage of the use of rubrics is that they are descriptive and rather than evaluative.

One of the operating principles of rubrics is to match the performance to the description rather than "judge" it. The main purpose of rubrics is to assess performances. Performances in educational setting refers to the observation of students in the process of doing a task like using an electric drill or discussing

an issue. Performance can be described as general or task specific.

Table 6. Tests of Between-Subjects Effects (Subject difficulty)

Source	Type III Sum of Squares				
	Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	128.815 ^a	40	3.220	5.490	.000
Intercept	206.343	1	206.343	351.748	.000
Lecture/Teacher Directed	4.274	4	1.068	1.821	.123
Individual Work	6.600	4	1.650	2.813	.025
Small Group	11.648	4	2.912	4.964	.001
Discussion/Small/Whole Class	7.951	4	1.988	3.388	.009
Activity/Lesson	4.679	4	1.170	1.994	.094
Computer/Internet/Tablet	5.040	4	1.260	2.148	.074
Film/DVD/Youtube	5.267	4	1.317	2.245	.063
Individual/Group/Presentation	16.476	4	4.119	7.022	.000
Demonstration/Experiment/Role Play	15.135	4	3.784	6.450	.000
Teacher-Question	6.862	4	1.715	2.924	.021
Error	339.654	579	.587		
Total	4083.000	620			
Corrected Total	468.469	619			

(DV: Subject Difficulty; a. R Squared = .275 (Adjusted R Squared = .225))

A general performance refers to the application of a whole tasks (e.g., writing, problem solving). It can be shared with students, explicitly linking assessment and instruction. In general performance, it may reuse the same rubrics with several tasks or assignments. It also supports learning by helping students to see "good work" as bigger than one task. It supports student self-evaluation and guide students to construct the rubrics. However, it has alower reliability at first than with task-specific rubrics.

A task-specific performance refers to the specific content of a particular task (e.g., gives an answer, specifies a conclusion). In this type of performance, scoring makes easier. It requires less time to achieve an inter-rater reliability. Compare to general performance, it cannot be shared with students. Also, it is challenging to write new rubrics for each task. For an open-ended task, good answers not listed in rubrics may be evaluated poorly.

According to Dietel, Herman and Ruth (1991) rubrics that have emphasis on assessment can be viewed in either cognitive or behavioral. Cognitive views include active, constructing knowledge- doing things and thinking, integrated and cross disciplinary, constituting discipline, use of skilled knowledge, procedural knowledge, attention to metacognition, understanding and analysis, assessments on multiple choice, multiple-choice test, high-tech applications, scientific application, multidimensional assessment and several angles or viewpoints. CLAS faculty were ask to identify trend stemming assessment under cognitive views.

According to the data collected, most of the rubrics dealt with accumulation of the isolated construct. With sixteen rubric items falling under this category, it is highly evident that educators in the Colegio prefer their students to obtain knowledge through their guidance and to process it themselves. Surprisingly, this method of assessment is followed from the area of social sciences (Sociology and Rizal Course), humanities, and the languages. However, this does not mean negligence from the part of the educators—it means that they allow the students to experience learning with minimal supervision, as opposed to a more teacher-centric

method of assessment, which received the lowest frequency in the collected data.

The paper and pencil assessment was met with little attraction from the educators because of its inherent traditionalism and rigidity. While it may work in the past, the future of curriculum development entails being more student-friendly and flexible for the challenges that they may meet after schooling. An objective kind of assessment may still be useful in some rubrics (i.e. Psychology subjects where theoretical mastery is imperative) but it is not the preferred method of the majority of the subjects where the rubrics came from.

In the behavioral level, the data shows that all the rubrics fell into more than one criterion, namely active constructing knowledge, integration and being cross-disciplinary, development of skills and knowledge, and multidimensional assessment. An overwhelming belief in these criteria exhibits parallelism of the educators in the Colegio in curriculum development fit for the 21st century. Aside from that, student to student and student to teacher collaboration are prioritized to suit the demands of integrative and multidimensional education. This focus on skills development and integration is what the Outcomes Based Education forwards, and it is what the educators in the Colegio practices, as evident in their rubrics.

What is interesting to note is that 21st century skills are one of the foundations of the OBE curriculum development and it entails the use of information and communication technology or ICT. The rubrics gathered by the researcher have very little correlation with the criteria of High-Tech Applications, perhaps because of the difficulty to exhaust materials and working knowledge to make use of it in education. While ICT and high-tech applications are useful in relaying information to students, the experiences of the educators, especially the more senior once, could be one of the challenges to be faced. So far, as the data portrays, the criteria of technology is not that practiced in the Colegio.

When it comes to the data about the syllabus, most, if not all, fell under the criterion of matching objectives to instructional program/curriculum. This means that the syllabi of the subjects in the Colegio follow suit to the guidelines set by the OBE curriculum development. In addition to that, majority of the subjects fell under that criteria because of the help of the institution to streamline OBE related methodologies in their faculty members. If majority of the syllabi follow the guidelines of the OBE, it means that the institution is doing a good job in joining the tides of the times when it comes to educational development.

On the flipside, the lowest in frequency is the criteria of understanding of world affairs. This is notable when it comes to the rigid sciences because it takes more effort to synthesize political world affairs in those subjects. Most of the syllabi that fell in this criteria belonged to the social and political sciences, with a few belonging to the field of psychology. This is a challenge for all subjects in the Colegio because international solidarity is one of the targets of the OBE curriculum development. Collaborative learning not just from the students of the same nationality but also exchange students

from other countries will cement the idea of a world where education is not hindered by geographic and political lines. Furthermore, an appreciation of world affairs from the perspective of the rigid sciences like biology, biochemistry, and mathematics may provide a new perspective in solving the world's problems (i.e. patents, development of drugs and medical sciences, architecture). This criteria should be given more focus in syllabi development, as well as in the development of the OBE curriculum and goals.

Tying these two together, we can deduce that the Colegio's educators are aware of the OBE curriculum development and that they had inculcated it in their rubrics and syllabi. As the data suggests, there may be several stumps that the faculty members experience in fulfilling the change brought about by the OBE but majority of the criteria were accomplished. Furthermore, these challenges in the OBE implementation only paves the way to the development of the OBE curriculum in itself. Dynamic reorientation between the administration and the faculty regarding OBE implementation must be reestablished.

The data collected by the researcher shows that the rubrics and the syllabi of the faculty members respond to the development of the curriculum and should be further improved to be more aligned to global demands. A globally competitive OBE syllabi and rubrics should be targeted to educate students in a global and holistic way, as what the OBE curriculum development is aiming. Constant monitoring of these outputs must be taken into consideration for better delivery of education to the learners.

The perception of the teachers and students were further validated through a classroom walkthrough and observation.

IV. CONCLUSION

In the Philippines, there is a shift in the curriculum from traditional teaching into Outcomes -Based Education (OBE). Among the institutions responding to the need in upgrading the bar in education is Colegio De San Juan De Letran (CSJL). Among the colleges in the colegio, the College of Liberal Arts and Sciences (CLAS) initiates the partial implementation of OBE in the seven programs under it, namely, AB Advertising, AB Broadcasting, AB Communication, AB Journalism, AB Legal Management, AB Political Science, and BS Psychology. In the partial implementation of OBE, all professors handling the subject under the said programs are required to implement OBE in paper, practice and pedagogy.

This study explores and analyzes the partial implementation of OBE under CLAS. The study sought to determine the perception of students and teachers towards OBE. It also describe the partial implementation of OBE in the area of: a. curriculum and instruction; b. teaching strategies; and c. assessment. It identified and described of the challenges and success of partial implementation of OBE in CLAS. The study draws out implications in the implementation of OBE policies.

Based on the results, the researchers concluded that CLAS faculty members have a positive attitude towards an outcomes-based educational approach and claimed to know how to do OBE in their respective classes. They agreed that

their schedule allows them to have an sufficient time to prepare for an OBE approach. Moreover, CLAS faculty members do a lot of readings to improve their knowledge and understanding of OBE.

They believe that OBE will raise the standard of students' academic achievement in their respective courses which can strengthen student's connections with the industry. They believe that OBE will give the flexibility in using different teaching methods in the class and that the new educational approach will allow equal educational opportunities for all students, success among all types of learners and will help enhance students' critical thinking, time management and productivity as the new approach is student-centered. CLAS faculty members feel that OBE is the best learning approach because the traditional assessment (pen-and-paper) does not always benefit the students. They feel satisfied with the current implementation of OBE, the students' performance, and their individual implementation of OBE in their respective classes.

However, when it comes to CLAS faculty member's knowledge about the assessment techniques for OBE, they felt that it is inadequate, CLAS faculty members feel that trainings provided in the past were not enough. CLAS faculty members also addressed that the Colegio should provide resources that support OBE's assessment especially when it comes to the creation of rubrics.

CLAS faculty members reported that they "rarely" use lecture/talk, discussion and question and answer as a form of teaching and student evaluation strategies in an OBE setup but when the students were asked about the different teaching and evaluation strategies that their professor used, students reported that their professor "always" used lecture and discussion. The student's perception contradicts the perception of the teachers towards the use of teaching strategy which is consistent with the result of scheduled class observations the teaching and learning strategies they used in their respective classes remained the same with that of the traditional teacher-centered approach. Majority of the class have passive listener and compliant in the requirements/tasks given by their professors.

It is important to establish high and uniform academic standards, accompanied by a system of accountability for the successful implementation of OBE. The Colegio should have a continuous and sustainable monitoring of the implementation of OBE during especially during its infancy.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The researchers acknowledge the financial support of Letran Research Center for the completion of this research endeavor.

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